

In well-reclaimed soil neither 10-cm nor 20-cm spacings yielded higher. During 1976 highest yield was at 15-cm spacing and 5 seedlings/ hill. Although general yield levels increased with plant populations and with soil improvement,

the difference in yield between the 2 best treatments (4 and 5 seedlings/ hill) narrowed to become statistically equal. Maximum grain yields of 6.5 and 6.6 t/ha during 1977 and 1978 were at 15-cm spacing and 4 seedlings/hill. 🌾

Effect of spacing and plant population (2, 3,4, and 5 seedlings/hill) on rice yield in partially and well-reclaimed alkali soils of Kumarganj (Faizabad), India.

Spacing (cm)	Gypsum ^a (t/ha)	Yield (t/ha)			
		2	3	4	5
<i>Pusa 2-21 (1976)</i>					
10	6	1.2	1.5	1.6	2.1
	12	1.2	1.6	1.8	2.2
15	6	1.0	1.3	1.7	2.1
	12	1.6	2.1	3.1	3.8
20	6	0.8	1.1	1.4	1.7
	12	1.5	1.9	2.2	2.7
LSD (0.05)		0.3			
<i>Java (1977)</i>					
10	6	4.3	4.7	5.1	5.5
	12	5.5	6.0	5.3	4.8
15	6	3.8	4.2	4.7	5.2
	12	5.1	5.5	6.5	6.3
20	6	3.5	3.9	4.3	4.6
	12	5.0	5.3	5.9	6.2
LSD (0.05)		0.5			
<i>Jaya (1978)</i>					
10	6	4.1	4.5	5.0	5.3
	12	5.3	5.6	5.4	4.8
15	6	3.6	4.0	4.5	4.9
	12	5.2	5.8	6.6	6.4
20	6	3.5	3.7	4.1	4.5
	12	4.9	5.3	5.7	6.1
LSD (0.05)		0.4			

^aGypsum was applied only once, in 1976.

Optimum spacing and nitrogen for medium-duration rice

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A 1982 experiment during samba (July-August to November-December) at PES, Tirur, showed that Ponni and IR20 yields increased at 20 × 20 cm rice plant spacing, regardless of the level of nitrogen applied (see table). 🌾

Effect of nitrogen levels and spacings on rice yield, Tirur, India, 1982 samba.

Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Ponni yield (t/ha)		IR20 yield (t/ha)	
	20 × 10 cm	20 × 20 cm	20 × 10 cm	20 × 20 cm
0	3.4	3.9	3.3	3.7
10	4.0	4.4	3.7	4.1
20	4.2	4.9	4.2	4.6
30	4.6	5.1	4.6	5.0
Mean	4.1	4.6	4.0	4.4
		CD	CD	
Nitrogen level	0.3**		0.2**	
Spacing	0.3**		0.2**	

Environment and its influence

Variations and associations in rice physiological growth parameters

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Grain productivity can be improved by using component breeding, which assumes productivity is associated with growth parameters and their heritability. Direct and indirect gene action related to productivity and growth traits should be known. This study hypothesizes level of improvement can be predicted by calculating the genetic coefficient of variation using heritability estimates.

Jaya, Kranti, JR 16-15-2, JR25-13-8, Madhuri, Garima, Ratna, Anupama, JR15-55-2, and IR36 were grown in a randomized block design with three replications at JNKVV Research Farm during July 1978-79. Growth parameters were evaluated every 2 weeks.

Physiological growth parameters among varieties varied significantly. Means of individual characteristics and the general mean also differed (Table 1). Coefficient of variation for genotype (gcv) ranged from 1.05 relative growth rate (RGR) to 25.99 leaf area ratio (LAR). Coefficient of variation for phenotype (pcv) ranged from 15.02 net assimilation rate (NAR) to 50.43 RGR. The gcv was equally higher in leaf area index (LAI) and crop growth rate (CGR), indicating the level of possible improvement.

Heritability values for all characteristics exhibited wide variations: range of 21.1 to 89.6. Heritability estimates were high for RGR followed by seed yield and leaf parameter (leaf weight ratio [LWR], LAR, and LAI). NAR and specific leaf area (SLA) had lower heritability values, reflecting environmental influence. Maximum genetic improvement was recorded for LAI and LAR

Positive, significant associations of LAI were recorded with leaf area dura-